

Using tree species and genetic diversity and epigenetic effects in UK woodland and forests to increase resilience

A research note produced by the Tree of Knowledge project, from the 'Future of UK Treescapes' programme.

**TREE OF
KNOWLEDGE**

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Summary highlights

- The aim of the research note is to identify the core qualities and interactions between species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects, and explore how forest managers might use this knowledge to enhance UK woodland and forest resilience to future threats.
- Our methodology involved collating knowledge via a synthesis workshop of 'Future of UK Treescapes' project leaders, project meetings, the 'Future Treescapes 24' conference and policymaker and practitioner workshops between 2023 and 2024.
- We highlight key issues and interactions among dimensions of diversity, and from this perspective discuss the challenges to achieving resilient woodlands and forests, which we qualify based on the literature and expert knowledge.
- Based on these interactions we identified three considerations for management, namely (1) the scale of achieving species diversity such as mixture designs of different species at a local scale versus separate blocks of species at a landscape scale; (2) promotion of natural colonisation and natural regeneration to support genetic adaptation, and (3) the role of nurseries in promoting species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects. We emphasise that all of these are context-specific and depend on woodland and forest type, manager objectives and cultural significances amongst many other factors.
- Finally, we identify key emerging policy implications for integrating these sources of diversity in planning for woodland and forest resilience. Topics identified include guidance and messaging, finance to support diversification, evaluating the success of diversification in achieving resilience, and key research and knowledge gaps.

Graphical summary

Table of contents

<u>1. Aim of research note.....</u>	<u>4</u>
<u>2. Concept of diversity.....</u>	<u>5</u>
<u>3. Potential benefits of species and genetic diversity and epigenetic effects for resilience.</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>3.1 Species diversity and resilience.....</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>3.2 Genetic diversity and resilience.....</u>	<u>7</u>
<u>3.3 Epigenetic effects and resilience.....</u>	<u>9</u>
<u>4. Interaction between species and genetic diversity and epigenetic effects.....</u>	<u>10</u>
<u>4.1 Species diversity and genetic diversity.....</u>	<u>10</u>
<u>4.2 Species diversity and epigenetic effects.....</u>	<u>11</u>
<u>4.3 Genetic diversity and epigenetic effects.....</u>	<u>11</u>
<u>5. Management considerations.....</u>	<u>12</u>
<u>5.1 At what spatial scale should species diversity and genetic diversity be managed?.....</u>	<u>13</u>
<u>5.2 Natural colonisation and natural regeneration to promote adaptation and epigenetic effects.....</u>	<u>14</u>
<u>5.3 Role of nurseries and management in promoting species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects.....</u>	<u>15</u>
<u>6. Policy implications.....</u>	<u>16</u>
<u>7. Acknowledgements.....</u>	<u>17</u>
<u>8. References.....</u>	<u>17</u>

1. Aim of the research note

Increasing diversity is a key part of the strategy to increase the general resilience of our woods and forests to a changing environment [1]. However, diversification is multi-layered: tree species diversity, within-species genetic diversity and within-individual epigenetic effects may all contribute to overall resilience of woodlands and forests. The aim of this research note is to identify the core qualities of each dimension of diversity, as well as their interactions, and explore how forest managers might make the best use of this knowledge to support resilient woodlands and forests. The research note is designed to act as a reference document with elements relevant to the practitioner, policymaker and the research community. This research note has been developed through the Tree of Knowledge project, which synthesised knowledge across three projects funded by UK Research and Innovation-Natural Environmental Research Council's 'Future of UK Treescapes' programme: MEMBRA¹, newLEAF and DiversiTree.

The methodology for this research note involved collating knowledge via a synthesis workshop of Treescapes project leaders, project meetings, the 'Future Treescapes 24' conference [2] and policymaker and practitioner workshops (workshops had 16 attendees from across DEFRA, NatureScot, Natural England, Confor and Institute of Chartered Foresters) between 2023 and 2024. To provide a level of certainty for the knowledge presented we sought feedback from experts across the three projects and, where appropriate, we have highlighted references and provided examples from on-going research. For brevity, emerging results are summarised and only the main sources of information are referenced. Where relevant, we also cite evidence from previous research identified by project team members.

We end with a short section on management considerations and policy implications, which has been developed with input from policymakers and practitioners. We highlight several potential options for diversifying woodlands and forests, noting that interventions will be context specific.

¹ The MEMBRA project stands for 'Understanding MEMory of UK Treescapes for Better Resilience and Adaptation' 4

2. Concept of diversity

This research note focuses on three sources of tree diversity that operate at different spatial scales from the individual tree to a region containing multiple woodlands and forests (Figure 1):

Species diversity is the number of different tree species found in a specified area e.g., stand, woodland or region.

Genetic diversity is the number of different genetic individuals (**genotypes**) found within one tree species, e.g. in stand, woodland or region. DNA contains genes, the expression of which determine the response of an individual to its environment. Individuals that have similar genetic make-up due to local adaptation to environmental conditions (e.g. climate, soil type, etc.) are referred to as a **provenance**.

Epigenetic effects are changes in the regulation of gene expression in response to the environment that does not involve changes to the DNA sequence. Epigenetic changes induced by environmental pressures during a plant's lifetime may be long-lasting [3, 4], hence epigenetic effects can be described as 'memory'. Alternatively, epigenetic effects may be lost once a stress no longer exists. Some epigenetic effects may be passed from mother trees to progeny.

Figure 1 Infographic showing different dimensions of diversity found in UK woodlands

Tree species differ across a wide range of characteristics, such as reproductive behaviour, physiology and growth. Differences in genetic make-up and epigenetic responses lead to ranges of variation in these characteristics within species. Species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects are all shaped by natural factors, including biology, ecology and environment, as well as by human interventions, e.g., selecting which tree species or provenance to plant.

Greater species and genetic diversity can be achieved in different ways depending on the spatial scale at which diversity is measured and managed. Spatially, diversity may be highly localised where a tree has immediate neighbours of different species, referred to in forestry as an mixed planting design (such as intimate mixtures) [5]; alternatively at a larger spatial scale several woodlands each composed of a single different tree species have low diversity within each woodland but high diversity overall across all the woodlands. The same is true for measures of genetic diversity. Epigenetic effects operate at the scale of the individual tree in response to environmental factors experienced within the lifetime of a tree; a single genotype experiencing different environments may show different characteristics due to epigenetic modification. Epigenetic effects may be evident spatially, if environments vary geographically, or temporally,

if trees experience different environments over time.

Here, we build upon previous work that focusses on the role of species diversity [6], and genetic diversity [7] to support woodland resilience in an era of environmental change.

3. Potential benefits of species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects for resilience

UK woodlands and forests need to be resilient to future threats, such as wind damage, drought, flooding, frost, pest, pathogens and wildfire [8]. Although there are many definitions of resilience, here we refer to **resilience** as the extent to which a system can absorb a disturbance, stress or shock [9], and not shift into another state [10, 11]. Similarly, in Biodiversity 2020, DEFRA defined resilience of an ecological system as its ability to ‘absorb, resist or recover from disturbance and damage...while continuing to meet overall objectives of supporting biodiversity and providing ecosystem services’ [12].

3.1. Species diversity and resilience

Tree species diversity has a central role in woodland and forest resilience [13]. The diversity-resilience relationship for trees is complex and our understanding is largely theoretical, but essentially, it should operate through three principal mechanisms: **bet-hedging**, **functional redundancy** and **dilution**.

- **Bet-hedging** is where the presence of multiple species insures against the loss of any one species, for example in a commercial setting growing two different species in productive forestry should reduce the chances that the entire timber crop is lost due to the impact of a pathogen that affects only one of them. In this case, the gain in resilience needs to be weighed against the change in productivity caused by a more diverse crop. This balance is at an optimum where productivity is at least maintained whilst resilience is increased, which may mean adding only a small number of species to the mixture.
- **Functional redundancy** arises when two species can deliver a similar function from the same environment. In this case, if one species is lost through a perturbation, such as disease or climate change, then the other will continue to support the functioning of the woodland or forest and associated biodiversity [14, 15]. The distinction between functional redundancy and bet-hedging is that functional redundancy requires species to have a strong overlap in functions and services (e.g., associated biodiversity) whereas this is not required with bet-hedging.
- **Dilution**, which is effective principally in the case of pests & diseases, and acts to mitigate the impact of the pest/disease by directly reducing the number of individual trees affected [16, 17], and by limiting the capability of the pest/disease to spread from tree to tree. However, this effect is dependent on the traits of the pest and pathogen and the species composition of the trees [18]. Emerging research is investigating whether greater tree species diversity affects the microbial diversity within leaves – the leaf microbiome – which may impact the response to pest and pathogens. This effect is likely to be contingent on the tree species, the phylogenetic relatedness of species in the woodland mixture, development age of stand, and site factors e.g., precipitation and herbivory (DiversiTree results).

In general, there is a great deal of uncertainty in the diversity-resilience relationship. Individual tree species, and consequently mixtures of tree species, may differ considerably in what they add to overall resilience. Emerging results from DiversiTree show that some tree species may provide greater resilience for tree-associated biodiversity than others. For example, few native trees will support most of the biodiversity hosted by Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), while most of the biodiversity supported by Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis*) in the UK is supported by a wide range of other tree species. Previous work has shown functional redundancy of different tree species differs for oak- and ash- associated biodiversity [19, 20]. Thus, increasing tree species diversity does not result in increased resilience for all tree-associated biodiversity, instead there is an important role of tree species identity. Moreover, different tree species will also respond differently to future threats [21], and the very fact of growing in mixtures may alter their response compared to trees in monocultures. Different strategies also come with contingent risks. For example, diversification with non-native but closely related species risks facilitating pests or pathogens either through direct introduction of a novel species, or by providing an additional, potentially more susceptible, host [40]. It also risks **hybridization** – interbreeding – between introduced and native species resulting in potential loss of vigour of native species [22, 23] or other unintended consequences.

Although the above cover the principal mechanisms, diversity may affect resilience in other ways. For example, higher tree species diversity may have indirect effects on resilience through greater structural diversity supporting associated biodiversity (e.g., forest birds [24]) and providing a more diverse range of timber products, market opportunities and amenity value [25]. The effects of diversification are complex and, though much has been done for foresters in developing mixed species approaches (see [Forest Development Types](#)), further research is merited to identify the optimal strategies for different objectives.

3.2 Genetic diversity and resilience

Genetic diversity is frequently referred to as the raw material of evolution but, as with species diversity, it may deliver resilience benefits in multiple ways. In an existing forest, the range of genetic types in a species is called the standing genetic diversity and this determines the immediate range of responses in a population. Adjusting the standing genetic diversity is the equivalent of the bet-hedging approach mentioned above for species diversity and may involve similar trade-offs. However, genetic diversity also provides adaptive potential for subsequent generations, as mating produces entirely new genetic combinations, and even existing genes will function differently in future new environments. These phenomena act on different timescales, the former determining outcomes in the present generation, whilst the latter determines outcomes in future generations and is contingent on a process of managed (deliberate selection, improvement or breeding) or natural (regeneration or recolonisation) gene transfer.

By maintaining genetic diversity, genotypes that may be sub-optimal in current environments persist and become optimal when conditions change. Genetic diversity is also a resource that can be drawn upon to improve key traits for production such as vigour, timber quality and pest and disease resistance [26]. As with species diversity, however, the diversity-resilience relationship is not linear: beyond a certain level, additional diversity may reduce overall resilience by introducing

sub-optimal genotypes.

Compared to ancient and semi-natural woodlands, the genetic diversity of certain traits can be narrower in commercial plantations, where certain productive genotypes have been deliberately selected and propagated to produce a uniform timber product with high yields. Although breeding programmes deliberately reduce genetic diversity, focussing on productive genotypes, there is broad awareness of the need to maintain genetic diversity to avoid inbreeding [27]. The use of genetic diversity in commercial plantations involves a trade-off between productivity/performance and resilience. Increasing the level of genetic diversity will introduce more productively sub-optimal genotypes, so reducing overall productivity/performance in the current environment. However, overall productivity may be maintained if the environment changes to become less suitable for current optimal genotypes and more suitable for the current sub-optimal genotypes. The choice of where to place the balance between productivity/performance and resilience depends strongly on the forester's evaluation, weighing the likely timing and severity of a threat against the time required for a forest to yield a product. Considering a single Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis*) rotation cycle, modelling suggests genetic diversity may be most beneficial when a threat is likely to be encountered early in the rotation cycle (Ewan McTaggart, Uni of Strathclyde, newLEAF, Future Treescapes 24 conference).

At a national or international scale, genetic variation within species can be a substantial resource for adaptation to future climate change and other threats [28] (Figure 2). Widespread local adaptation within species means matching tree provenance to planting sites is widely recommended. This should ensure persistence in the current climates that young trees will live through, although there is much concern now over whether these approaches may fail to account for the scale of future climatic shifts. Augmenting genetic diversity through **assisted gene flow** [29] (also termed **assisted migration** [30]) aims to introduce future-adapted genotypes by deliberately importing provenances from sites in which current conditions match those predicted in future at the planting site [7]. However, assisted gene flow/ migration approaches carry the substantial risk of introducing maladaptation, with the potential for failure of introduced non-local provenances [31], especially at early life stages. If carried out at scale, assisted gene flow may homogenise genetics at a landscape scale and reduce the genetic distinctiveness of specific populations [32]. There is also a question of the extent to which future conditions can be accurately forecast, given the range of factors affecting local adaptation in trees. Finally, interventions to assist gene dispersal also downplay the natural ability of tree species to disperse. Most northern temperate and boreal tree species have wind-dispersed pollen (and often seed) with high mobility. Thus, regular incorporation of non-local genetic diversity is already a natural part of the way populations of tree species function.

Utilizing within-species genetic diversity in the UK to build resilient forests

Figure 2. Infographic displaying breadth of trait variation in relation genetic variation across the UK climate and how different forest management options shape genetic diversity.

3.3 Epigenetic effects and resilience

Awareness of the potential benefits of epigenetic effects for woodland and forest resilience is low, as the epigenetic responses of trees is an emerging area of research [33, 34]. Epigenetic effects are dynamic and allow individual trees to respond to current stresses due to environmental change [3]. For instance, the MEMBRA project has identified epigenetic changes in ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) in response to ash dieback disease and in trees of oak species (*Quercus spp.*) to acute oak decline, drought and CO₂ stimulation (unpublished results), demonstrating clear differences in the impact of stress in trees at different developmental stages. MEMBRA is further exploring the concept of tree immunisation (tree equivalent to vaccination) by inducing epigenetic changes that are retained as ‘memory’ in planting stock. This could be achieved by priming tree seedlings in nurseries, exposing seedlings to a stress using chemicals or other stimuli to induce epigenetic changes to increase immediate and future resilience of individual trees [35]. Whilst evidence for priming epigenetic effects have been observed in other plants, there are questions about whether trees can be primed, the mechanisms that result in priming and how long responses to primed stresses last. Preliminary results suggest oak seedlings can be primed for defence against powdery mildew [36] and elder (*Sambucus nigra*) cuttings can be primed to drought stress using chemical stimuli [37].

4. Key issues and interactions between species and genetic diversity and epigenetic effects

Below we identify interactions between species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects. Interactions are grouped into either: **positive** – where outcomes are favourable or sources of diversity complement one another in achieving woodland and forest resilience, or **negative** – where outcomes are unfavourable, or sources of diversity are not complementary and/or management decisions need to prioritise one source of diversity over another. We qualify each example with the level of supporting evidence (literature, expert knowledge, emerging results or hypotheses) and the degree of confidence expressed by experts (high, medium or low).

4.1 Species diversity and genetic diversity

Positive:

- High species diversity and genetic diversity can reduce the impacts of some pests and pathogens via a dilution effect, in other words reducing the prevalence of a pest/disease because only a proportion of species will be susceptible or hosts [Evidence: literature [17, 18, 38-41] | Confidence: medium-high].
- Species diverse woods and forests, where tree species compete with one another, may promote competitive and/or ecologically complementary genotypes [Evidence: literature on tree growth [42] and natural disturbance resistance [43] | Confidence: medium].
- For a given species, a higher level of genetic diversity will raise the probability that a species will withstand a stress or pest/disease stress tolerance, but can involve severe loss [Evidence: literature [44] | Confidence: low-medium].

Negative:

- In a woodland or forest area with a finite number of trees, there will be a trade-off between species diversity and genetic diversity. This can be thought of as an ‘opportunity cost’, where each tree of one species that is present means one tree of another is not. Although this is an unavoidable trade-off in any mixed-species scenario, it may be particularly acute where non-native species are used at the expense of native species, where a larger population of the native species may be seen as contributing more to the wider national gene pool [Evidence: expert knowledge | Confidence: high].
- Focussing on species diversification may lead to more short-term resilience but not ensure the longer-term resilience of woodlands and forests. For example, the introduction of new species may be a quicker, cheaper and more easily ‘visible’ route to enhancing the resilience of woodlands than building the resilience of a species already present. But the introduction of new species (or genotypes) to a woodland has associated and often unforeseen risks, such as introducing or facilitating pests or pathogens, or resulting in maladaptation to current or future climate conditions. The introduction of non-native pine species (*Pinus contorta* and *P. nigra*) to the UK has been shown to have led to the introduction of a non-native race of the pathogen *Dothistroma septosporum*, which is impacting on native Scots pine [45]. As native pathogen races are already present, there is also the added potential that hybridisation between the native and introduced races generates more aggressive pathogen races [Evidence: literature [45, 46] | Confidence: low-medium].

- If increased tree species diversity leads to introduction of non-native species that are closely related to native species there is a risk of hybridization and subsequent changes to the genetic variation of the native species. This could potentially also be a route to introducing new genetic diversity [Evidence: literature [47] | Confidence: low-mixed outcome].

4.2 Species diversity and epigenetic effects

Positive:

- Epigenetic effects can widen a tree species stress tolerance [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research and Epidiverse project [48, 49] | Level of confidence: Medium].
- The importance of epigenetic effects differs between tree species and can be used selectively to increase the resilience of target species e.g. to increase resilience of ash trees to ash dieback disease [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research | Level of confidence: Medium].

Negative:

- The magnitude of epigenetic effects differs between tree species; therefore, promoting epigenetic effects will be less beneficial for some species compared to others e.g. response to drought and rising atmospheric CO₂ concentration in different tree species [Knowledge base: MEMBRA results | Level of confidence: High].
- Epigenetic changes to past stresses can lead to disadvantageous plant characteristics and some species being outcompeted in mixtures e.g. insect defoliation stress and drought stress [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research | Level of confidence: Low].
- Species diverse woodlands and forests may lower the stress experienced by individual trees and thus weaken the epigenetic response to the stresses [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research - hypothesis | Level of confidence: Low].

4.3 Genetic diversity and epigenetic effects

Positive:

- The combination of genetic diversity and epigenetic effects can provide a deeper level of resilience as they can operate at different temporal scales. Standing genetic diversity determines the immediate range of response in a population, whilst genetic change over generations determines the scale of adaptive response over time. Epigenetic effects operate at the single tree level and can occur within the lifespan of a tree. Thus, in combination, genetic diversity and epigenetic responses allow both long- and short-term response to a stress [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research e.g. study of genetic diversity within stressed individuals | Level of confidence: Low].
- Some stresses may lead to genetic responses but not epigenetic responses and vice versa. There can be some complementarity in making use of both dimensions of diversity in responding to future stresses [Knowledge base: hypothesis | Level of confidence: Low].
- With increasing levels of genetic diversity, there will be increasing variation in the impact of a given stress on individual trees and consequently in the range of epigenetic response [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research e.g. genetic diversity within individuals | Level of confidence: Low – replication needs to be increased].

- Epigenetic changes affect patterns of genetic change in populations of well-studied plants, but whether this occurs for trees is still being explored [Knowledge base: literature in model plants [50]; follow-up hypothesis of MEMBRA | Level of confidence: Low].

Negative:

- There are concerns that genetic adaptation of populations to future threats will be too slow to ensure survival [7] or that UK genetic resources will be insufficient [31], given the expected rate of climate change. Prioritising measures that would favour epigenetics, e.g., priming of individuals, rather than genetic turnover, may be a more rapid way to provide resilience to immediate future threats. Uncertainty over whether prioritising epigenetics would inhibit longer-term genetic adaptation [Knowledge base: MEMBRA ongoing research | Level of confidence: Low-medium]
- Epigenetic effects can buffer populations against the selection pressure that would facilitate genetic adaptation to a stress. In other words, epigenetic effects can alter the selective environment, such that individual trees that have genotypes ill-adapted to a stress can survive due to epigenetic responses [Knowledge base: Hypothesis | Level of confidence: Low].
- Epigenetic memory of a stress that no longer exists may inhibit the process of genetic adaptation [Knowledge base: hypothesis | Level of confidence: Low].

5. Management considerations

Before detailing management considerations, for practitioners intending to diversify woodlands there are some general points to consider: (1) diversifying woodlands will not always equate to a greater resilience to future threats, for example tree diversity experiments in Germany have shown higher tree mortality following drought, highlighting the importance of selecting drought tolerant tree species as opposed to higher diversity *per se* [51]; (2) whatever approach to diversification is taken the principle should always be to maintain within-species genetic diversity, to allow a range of responses to current and future environmental conditions; (3) diversification may involve making challenging decisions and a degree of failure, for example there may be higher mortality of ill-adapted species or genotypes, and there may ultimately be a trade-off between resilience and performance/productivity. However, the potential cost of not diversifying may be greater.

In the UK, the commercial forestry sector is currently dominated by a single non-native conifer species – Sitka spruce – and, despite growing interest in broadening species diversity, change will take time [52]. A key question is: how much diversity is enough? Of course there is no single answer, and northern temperate and boreal woodlands have naturally low species numbers compared to the tropics, but it is reasonable to ask if adding more species to forests than they had prior to human intervention would help to ensure resilience to future threats? If so, which tree species and how many are required?

For all management implications outlined below we wish to emphasise these are context specific, and their efficacy depends upon on woodland and forest type, land manager objectives and

cultural significances amongst many other factors. It is also important that managers develop a clear, operational understanding of resilience for their context: consider what needs to be resilient (e.g., a particular species, or an ecosystem service like timber production), and to what pressure (e.g., a particular disease, or increased drought), bearing these considerations in mind will make choices regarding diversification clearer.

5.1 At what spatial scale should species diversity and genetic diversity be managed?

Diversity can be considered at different spatial scales. For example, a single forest stand may contain several species or only one; yet, at a larger spatial scale a landscape filled with stands of the former is no more diverse than the one filled with multiple single species stands each comprised of different species. There are many ways to manage woodlands to enable diversity: Forest Research have produced guidance on Forest Development Types to help planners and practitioners decide about species diversification at multiple spatial scales, different aged stands and species mixes [53]. Below we outline two broad approaches to increase species or genetic diversity at different spatial scales (Figure 3):

- A *mixture design* of two or more tree species in close proximity (such as an intimate mixture) achieves higher species diversity at a local scale, because each tree is likely to have neighbours of a different species. Reviews of literature identify mixed forests are more resilient than monocultures on average to small mammal herbivores, soil-borne fungal diseases and specialised insect herbivores but effects are contingent on species composition amongst other factors [18, 43]. Admixing broadleaves to conifer stands can also increase resistance to fire and windstorm pressures when compared to conifer monocultures [43]. However, the benefits of mixed stands for threats such as drought are less clear and depend on species in the mixture, for example in the UK intimate mixes of Sitka spruce and Scots pine, of differing proportions, did not result in greater resilience to spring drought compared to monocultures when comparing growth at 24 years in the tree crop rotation [21]. Managing mixture designs can be logistically challenging and costly if one species within the mix needs to be removed following a statutory plant health order (DiversiTree practitioner panel meeting). The UK commercial harvesting and timber processing

Figure 3. Infographic depicting different spatial scales in which tree species (and genetic) diversity can be achieved through planting designs.

systems are better able to manage uniform products as opposed to diverse timber products from mixture planting designs; however, plantings will not be harvested for several decades, which gives the harvesting and timber processing sectors time to adapt.

- *Separate blocks* of different single species result in diversification at a larger spatial scale. Many of the tree species that provide the greatest benefit to tree-associated biodiversity do not grow in mixed planting designs with Sitka spruce. Therefore, planting separate blocks of different single species may provide a suitable alternative [5]. This has been recommended for diversification of Sitka spruce by DiversiTree [54]. As a method for diversification of Sitka spruce plantations, blocking could also introduce a second species unlikely to be affected by the primary threats to Sitka, providing some resilience of timber supply. Potentially, such diversification could also reduce spread of pest and diseases threatening Sitka, although attention would have to be paid to dispersal mechanisms of pest and diseases to ensure appropriate block structure and design. Finally, planting in blocks aligns with current UK conifer harvesting and timber processing practices. Removal of a species following a statutory plant health order will be less costly but would result in complete loss of the canopy in that block and require restocking.

5.2 Natural colonisation and natural regeneration to promote adaptation and epigenetic effects

Natural woodland creation and expansion relies primarily on natural colonisation. The process operates where trees self-seed onto open ground (formally, ground that has not been wooded for the past 20 years). Natural regeneration refers to the same process but in existing woodland [55]. In contrast to tree planting, natural colonisation and regeneration allow natural selection to operate in determining which species and genotypes establish on a site. The 'Future of UK Treescapes' project TreE PlaNat addresses the ecological resilience of natural colonisation with findings that mixed natural colonisation and tree planting sites have higher tree-associated biodiversity levels (e.g., flora and moths) and lower insect herbivory compared to tree planting or natural colonisation only sites. Supporting natural colonisation and regeneration may require removal of barriers to tree establishment, such as gap creation or reducing herbivore pressure. A key point of failure in relying on natural processes would be if climate change or other future threats impact reproduction. Below we focus on how natural colonisation and regeneration can support species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects and therefore the resilience of woodlands and forests:

- *Species diversity*: Natural colonisation and regeneration can increase species diversity on open ground when seed sources are nearby. Within woodlands, natural regeneration allows for the reorganisation of species composition, to best suit the environmental and management conditions [56]. However, natural colonisation and regeneration can result in a single species or low species diversity of seedlings depending on the diversity of seed sources available, competitive interactions between tree species and herbivores impacts dependent on tree palatability of tree species.
- *Genetic diversity*: Natural colonisation and regeneration enables natural selection to optimise genotypes to environmental conditions [57]. As selection is likely to be very strong in early life stages, the process has the potential to track rapidly changing environments if sufficient genetic diversity is available and generational turnover happens quickly enough. Due to effective pollen dispersal, even small populations can produce genetically diverse seed crops.

Natural colonisation and regeneration can be a slow process if seed sources are remote or small and herbivore pressure is high. There are concerns that environmental changes may occur too rapidly for local populations to adapt if recruitment opportunities are limited [7].

- *Epigenetic effects*: Using natural colonisation and regeneration to promote epigenetic effects can involve retaining stressed trees to allow them to set seed and, if the epigenetic changes are inherited, pass those on to the next generation. This would confer epigenetic-based tolerance on subsequent generations of trees, an effect that appears to be occurring in the ash dieback and Acute Oak Decline epidemics (MEMBRA provisional results). The balance between removal and retention should be considered when introduced diseases become endemic. The latter may better suit managers when the objective is woodland recovery as opposed to timber production. Statutory plant health removal notices should be followed for high-risk pathogens and pests as the aim is to eliminate or significantly slow the spread of the disease.

5.3 Role of nurseries in promoting species diversity, genetic diversity and epigenetic effects

Nursery supply is dictated by demand and if there is a growing interest in diversifying woodlands, nurseries will diversify their stock. Currently nurseries play an important role in ensuring diverse sources of species and provenances and, in addition, there is the potential to harness epigenetic effects. Nevertheless, it is important to recognise that nurseries in the UK are already under pressure to meet the demand for trees associated with woodland expansion targets and that they need security of funding with respect to rearing trees in advance of large projects. If guidance on species diversity, genetic diversity or epigenetic effects changes at short notice this can have huge financial implications and implication for the supply of trees [58].

- *Seed supply* chains that sample widely can support higher species diversity and genetic diversity and will need to be sustained to maintain diverse seed availability. Some species have traits (masting, recalcitrance) that make seed collection harder, and obtaining and maintaining supplies of a wide range of provenances may not be financially viable; seed stands and orchards can help to ameliorate these issues [58, 59].
- *On-site nurseries* allow tree stock to be raised within the local environmental conditions in which they will be planted and should promote the trees most suited to the site's current climatic conditions.
- *The nursery environment* itself can have large and lasting impacts on tree growth and survival even after the trees are planted out. newLEAF research on Scots pine showed that the effects of different nursery environments, such as outdoor versus glasshouse rearing, are detectable in height differences more than a decade after planting in the field [60]. Epigenetic changes can potentially be induced within a nursery by exposing seedlings to stress or chemical treatments that will increase their resilience to these stresses when planted out. However, further work is required to assess the practicalities, to ensure stressed trees do not present a disease risk, and to assess customer attitudes towards buying deliberately stressed trees.

6. Policy implications

The interactions between species diversity and genetic diversity and epigenetic effects have not previously been considered in policy. Thus, much of the information within this research note is new or emerging research and many of the implications for policy need further consideration. However, the following implications for policy have already emerged:

- *Guidance and messaging*: The effects of species diversity and genetic diversity are highly context dependent. While species and genetic diversification can have positive effects on woodland and forest resilience, diversification does not necessarily equate to resilience. There can be qualities of individual species or genotypes that surpass the effects of diversity, per se, in ensuring resilience. As an emerging research area tree epigenetics does not yet have clear policy implications, nevertheless it seems likely that epigenetics will be a future part of a suite of tools for woodland and forest resilience.
- *Finance to support diversification*: influencing how practitioners manage woodlands and what they plant through grants is challenging, because if the stipulated species or genotypes do not meet practitioners' requirements then they will not apply for a grant. Grants that support natural processes, namely natural colonisation and regeneration, offer the opportunity to work with diversity and maintain processes integral to woodlands and forests. There are some grants available to support woodland expansion by natural colonisation, e.g., [England Woodland Creation Offer](#) although there is scope for integrating better evaluation criteria to monitor species and genetic diversity.
- *Evaluation of success*: How to determine if diversification has been 'successful' in increasing woodland and forest resilience? Forest Research have produced comprehensive guidance on [Forest Development Types](#), but these guidelines do not link diversification action with resilience outcomes. Research is needed to develop indicators that could evaluate resilience, but resilience may only be measurable on decadal to century timescales.
- *Planning for resilience*: For example, NatureScot is exploring ways to develop a risk assessment for their woodland sites, asking managers to think about future risks and what they can do to mitigate them (NatureScot pers. comms.).
- *Research/knowledge gaps*: There are multiple research gaps related to diversification and resilience. These include:
 - Yield versus diversity trade-off in production forestry.
 - Attitudes / preferences of timber producers towards diversification.
 - Interaction between structural diversity and species diversity or genetic diversity.
 - Interaction between epigenetic change and genetic adaptation.
 - Extent to which tree diversification affects associated biodiversity, for example, interactions between tree diversity and soil biodiversity, particularly fungal symbionts.
 - How to support long-term monitoring; required as trees are long-lived organisms and interactions between species and genetic diversity and epigenetic effects take time to be detected.

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